

FARCLIMATE

DELIVERABLE D3.1 Characterisation of Case Studies: Guidelines and Indicators

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List of acronyms

EC: European Commission

EU: European Union

FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization [of the United Nations]

KPI: Key Performance Indicators

LL: Living Lab

NbS: Nature-based Solutions

NGO: Non-Governmental Organisation

NUTS: Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics

SAFA: Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture

SME: Small and Medium Enterprise

UN: United Nations

VC: Value Chain

WP: Work Package

Project information

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Abstract:	<p>This deliverable outlines guidelines and indicators for WP3. First, it details a value-based characterisation methodology for coordinating the inception of climate change adaptation strategies for local/regional value chains. It employs a reflective, value-based approach to analyse current and future scenarios in the value chain. This characterisation aims to inform policy and coordination recommendations to FARCLIMATE case studies (WP6), all in coordination with the Living Lab methodology that case studies follow (WP2). Furthermore, the deliverable presents a method for supporting business modelling for climate change adaptation, designed to help socially and environmentally oriented enterprises develop climate change adaptation strategies. This framework integrates existing tools, centred on the Business Model Canvas, to blend business within adaptation modelling. Finally, the deliverable proposes a pre-selection of self-assessment indicators for use in the case studies and statistical indicators for WP3 tasks. These indicators aim to support the evaluation of climate adaptation initiatives at various levels and inform broader project activities.</p>

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Executive Summary

FARCLIMATE is a Horizon Europe project that aims to implement transformative solutions on the path to climate resilience, in line with the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. Economic sectors affected by climate change need to be transformed to face the existing risks and develop climate-resilient business models and value chains. Re-skilling opportunities need to be available, and national, regional and local governments must play an active role in the transition to climate resilience. Socially accepted and sustainable solutions also need to be pursued. FARCLIMATE aims to implement transformative solutions on the path to climate resilience in at least 20 regions and communities across Europe, in line with the EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. It will address the complex challenges of developing and expanding climate-resilient measures, making them available and understandable to everyone, while also paying special attention to the social, political and economic barriers commonly found.

European regions and local communities are setting up case studies with the assistance of FARCLIMATE to create, together, innovations in climate resilience and climate change adaptation in the agriculture, silviculture and fishing sectors. The case studies are implemented as living labs: open innovation ecosystems in which different stakeholders work together to co-create solutions to relevant problems in their community. Our mission is to help case studies launch a successful living lab in their local community and gain the empowerment and skills to develop local solutions for climate change adaptation.

We are pursuing advancements in climate change resilience and adaptation such as:

- Socioeconomic analysis of the communities in the context of climate change adaptation.
- Training to empower the different local stakeholders in climate change adaptation.
- A communication strategy that conveys the message that we all can work together for a climate-resilient future.
- Policy recommendations, business models and strategies for climate change adaptation.
- Creation of a European network of climate-resilient communities.

The backbone of FARCLIMATE case studies is the Living Lab methodology for developing the case study communities (WP2 deliverables) and the sectoral climate adaptation solution-seeking methodologies (T3.6 and WP5). In other words, these activities are the ones around which we orchestrate most of the rest of FARCLIMATE activities. Under this frame, D3.1 presents three complementary contributions to advancing the FARCLIMATE approach at the local/regional value chain level.

The three contributions of this deliverable should also be understood under the overall purpose of WP3, which is to provide the overall characterisation of the value chains, in the context of climate change adaptation. Specifically, T3.2 provides an economic characterisation of the value chains—addressing business, economic and financial aspects; T3.3 characterisation takes a more socioeconomic perspective, focusing on aspects such as employment or well-being. T3.4 characterisation is conducted to understand consumer behaviour and behavioural change. T3.5 provides an environmental characterisation including, e.g., the alignment with the EU Taxonomy and an ecosystem service analysis. Finally, T3.6 provides the methodology for

seeking innovative solutions within FARCLIMATE's three core sectors: agriculture, forestry and fishery.

First, the [value-based characterisation methodology](#) of Section 1 aims to coordinate the inception of climate change adaptation strategies at the overall local/regional value chains. It can be embedded in the Living Lab approach as the activity to define the policy or coordination recommendations for the value chain ecosystem (WP6). For this goal, we step back and apply a reflective value-based approach to understand and produce a picture of what is happening, what ought to happen and how we make it happen. This characterisation methodology aims to provide a conceptual framework to help communities reflect the underpinnings of their worldview regarding what to do to drive or foster climate change adaptation in their local/regional value chain. As such, this deliverable's general object of study and intervention are the local value chains of the case studies, examining them in two distinct phases: the current and the new value chain.

Then, the method for supporting [business modelling for climate change adaptation](#) in Section 2 seeks to be relevant for designing the strategy of socially and environmentally oriented enterprises. This framework integrates existing tools, pivoting around the Business Model Canvas, bridging the domains of business modelling and climate change adaptation, and offering a structured yet flexible approach for combining business and adaptation modelling logic.

Finally, Section 3 presents a [preselection of indicators](#) for the case studies and WP3. On the one hand, self-assessment indicators that the Living Lab or other entities in the case studies could use to assess their own progress in their climate adaptation initiatives, projects or even at their organisations. These are a selection from indicators developed in D3.7 for a more detailed analysis of the value chains and from indicators related to Nature-based Solutions or other IUCN standards (WP5). On the other hand, statistical indicators, at NUTS3 level or more granular, which are available in Eurostat or that could potentially be found in regional/national statistical databases. They came partly from the case study selection criteria (D2.2). These statistical indicators could be helpful in the rest of the WP3 tasks.

Figure 11 represents the relation of the previous three contributions with the FARCLIMATE case studies' Living Labs and other WP3 developments.

Figure 1. Relation of the methodologies proposed in this deliverable and the Living Labs.

1. Value-based methodology for the characterisation of the value chains of the case studies

1.1 Rationale of the value-based characterisation methodology

Climate change raises new challenges (IPCC, 2022) that require new perspectives, so sustainable development practices and climate adaptation policies can reinforce each other to create climate-resilient territories. This effort demands a multiple-viewpoint approach through the involvement of stakeholders to bring focus on the problem and develop integrative models for governing and developing sustainable and resilient solutions (Beretic et al., 2024). Furthermore, these new circumstances call for interdisciplinarity (Wamsler et al., 2021) and the adoption of a top-down and bottom-up collaborative approach (Dzebo et al., 2019), where both policymakers and people experiencing the impacts can share their views and problems and find common spaces for co-creation. It is an exercise of social innovation and evidence-based policy generation toward environmental adaptation (Müller et al., 2021) through case studies, small-scale pilots or community initiatives.

Dealing with those challenges is a preliminary step to adapting regions and production systems to new climatic realities. This should necessarily start through an approach where the different stakeholders participating should feel comfortable and perceive their involvement as rewarding.

For this goal, stepping back to an applied philosophical reflection is recommended to understand and produce a picture of what is happening, what ought to happen and how we make it happen. That is, we should be able to create the best figure with the highest qualified consensus possible. Likewise, this figure can benefit from experiences in other regions. Still, it should be prepared for the particular realities of each region and for empowering the local communities to tackle climate adaptation. This value-based characterisation methodology aims to provide a conceptual framework to help communities reflect the underpinnings and drive climate change scenarios.

1.2 Object of study of the value-based characterisation methodology

Value chains are evolving towards new business models. As such, this process should be understood to help those value chains steer this transformation towards one aimed at climate change adaptation.

As such, the general object of study and intervention of this deliverable are the local value chains (VCs) of the case studies, examining them in two distinct phases:

- The current value chain (Current VC).
- The new value chain (New VC), based on a prospective scenario.

While the prospective scenario can be adapted to various analyses and timeframes, its application within the FARCLIMATE case studies requires a more focused approach. Our LL participants—businesses, professionals and sector organisations—are primarily concerned with, and capable of influencing, developments in the coming years and medium term. Consequently, a scenario centred around the mid-2030s is most appropriate. Furthermore, we also consider that the transformations within this prospective scenario, encompassing both value chain and

climate change considerations, are firmly grounded in current trends identified by the LL participants.

1.3 Theoretical grounds of the value-based characterisation methodology

1.3.1 Organisational and management theories

The approach of the value-based characterisation methodology is grounded in, and integrates, diverse ideas from diverse organisational and managerial theories that we found relevant in the domain of co-creation for climate change adaptation. We summarise these insights in Table 11.

Theory	Key insights for the characterisation methodology
Stakeholder Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foster cooperative relationships with stakeholders by balancing interests (Freeman et al., 2010), through complex equilibriums (Freeman et al., 2010; Jones, 1995). • Incorporate explicitly an economic dimension (value creation), a social dimension (managing relationships) and a moral dimension (fairness) (Bridoux & Stoelhorst, 2022).
Social Exchange Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focus on the nature of human relationships dynamics (Kalra et al., 2024). • Assumptions (West & Turner, 2017): People (1) tend to seek out rewards and avoid punishments, (2) begin interactions to gain maximum profit with minimal cost, (3) calculate the profit and cost before engaging and (4) know that this payoff will vary from person to person and over time.
Contingency Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Courses of action are contingent (dependent) upon the internal and external situation. Contingency, rooted in multiple unknown influencing factors, might cause uncontrollable and unpredictable events, including the potential to overcome lock-ins or established paths (Schikowitz et al., 2023). • Contingency is an adequate approach to deal with the complexity of sustainability (Broccardo et al., 2023), where the alignment between an organisation and its context is core to its success (Donaldson, 2001).
Actor-Network Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Any isolated perspective, including social and technological determinisms, tends to fail (Marcon Nora, 2023). • Actors, as essential in this process, are defined based on their role, how active they are, how repercussive they are and how much effect they produce in the network (Latour, 2012).
Dynamic Capabilities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dynamic capabilities are the organisation's abilities to purposefully adapt internal and external resources and competences to address and shape rapidly changing environments. • Dynamic capabilities make it possible to identify strategic and organisational practices, principles and routines required to sense (understand what is going on), seize (identify opportunities to act upon) and transform (integrate, build and reconfigure internal and external capabilities to seize the opportunity) (Teece, 2007). This allows the acquisition of new resources and competences for coping with highly changing environments (Eisenhardt & Martin, 2000). • A dynamic capability approach is well-suited for evaluating emergent niche opportunities, particularly to adapt to new realities (Wang & Hsu, 2018).

Theory	Key insights for the characterisation methodology
"Power School of Strategy"	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Authors like Allison, Astley, Pfeffer and Salancik emphasise the role of power dynamics, influence, conflicts, negotiations and coalition-building in forming strategies and resource allocation (Mintzberg et al., 2009).

Table 1: Insights from organisational and managerial theories for our value-based characterisation methodology.

1.3.2 Philosophical underpinnings

The value-based characterisation aims to facilitate adaptive governance of the situation of the VC and its key actors, emphasising not only the interconnectedness of social, technical and environmental systems, but the interconnectedness of these elements with more fundamental concepts, reflections, decisions and, ultimately, values.

This intertwining requires a philosophically grounded approach (via ontology, axiology, epistemology, etc.) to operate at a meta-managerial, organisational and governance level. Grounding decisions in philosophical domains (ontology, axiology, etc.) helps us ensure ethical coherence, contextual adaptability, and value-driven action across socio-technical systems. However, the approach shall also operate as a bottom-up, participatory praxis to characterise case studies. In a way that it is built and connects with the LL approach we propose in WP2. This blends critical realism (acknowledging layered realities shaped by power and values), pragmatic ethics (action guided by context-specific moral stakes) and the participatory, community-driven action provided by the LL. It is "meta" in structure but bottom-up in praxis, ensuring systemic rigour without divorcing analysis from lived experience.

Moreover, this value-based approach systematically integrates stakeholder values, ethical priorities, and contextual dynamics into decision-making for climate adaptation in local VCs. Value-based approaches typically focus on the underlying values that drive decisions and interactions. As such, the value-based approach is the core lens through which each step of our characterisation is driven and decisions are made.

The notion of value is multifaceted, and its interpretation varies across disciplines. Understanding these distinctions is critical in a project like FARCLIMATE, which addresses economic, environmental and social aspects. While economic value often dominates discussions, broader philosophical and socio-ecological interpretations are equally vital. Clarifying these concepts ensures stakeholders align priorities, whether measuring climate responses, ethical responsibilities, or community well-being.

Economic theories on value traditionally define it through labour, scarcity, utility or exchange. In management, the study of value is influenced by those economic perspectives. However, managerial and organisational research is traditionally more pluralistic than Economics, incorporating aspects of other social sciences. It also involves more applied research to identify key factors or approaches for making organisations more successful. Although the concept of value creation has its basis in Economics, it has become more important in the applied context of business management (Zott et al., 2011). The concept of value-creation centres on delivering benefits to stakeholders while sustaining a competitive advantage that enables the organisation to make a profit or at least sustain its activities. Modern views on value creation increasingly prioritise shared value, blending profit with societal impact.

Philosophy explores value as a fundamental concept, reflecting on what qualities make something worthy, good, important or any other value. It distinguishes intrinsic value (worth inherent to an entity, such as human dignity) from instrumental value (derived from utility, like

forests mitigating climate change). Ethical theories further emphasise normative aspects of values: e.g., deontologists stress moral duty, while utilitarians prioritise outcomes. Aesthetic, cultural, and spiritual values also shape human priorities. It is within philosophy where the more fundamental values, such as goodness or justice, are analysed. The philosophical field that studies values is called Axiology.

We can also talk about social value, which emphasises collective well-being, partially quantified through metrics like quality of life or equity. Ecological value, meanwhile, assigns worth to ecosystems and biodiversity, transcending monetary terms. For FARCLIMATE, embedding such principles ensures projects like reforestation address not just monetary-measurable targets but also biodiversity loss and local livelihoods. Table 22 displays some of the most common values globally.

In FARCLIMATE, we deal not only with economic value concepts but also with a broader set of values. The question of how general values interact with the more economic perspective of value creation is essential; for instance, value-creation frameworks that may sustain fairness and sustainability (Donaldson, 2021).

1 Family	15 Respect	29 Friendships	43 Dependability
2 Relationships	16 Compassion	30 Authority	44 Courage
3 Financial Security	17 Social Standing	31 Positive Environments	45 Cooperation
4 Belonging	18 Creativity & Imagination	32 Happiness	46 Tolerance
5 Community	19 Trustworthiness/Honesty	33 Ambition	47 Leisure
6 Personal Growth	20 Security	34 Self-Control	48 Influence
7 Loyalty	21 Education	35 Self-Expression	49 Intimacy
8 Religion/Spirituality	22 Tradition	36 Environmentalism	50 Political Freedom
9 Employment Security	23 Balance	37 Independence	51 Peace
10 Personal Responsibility	24 Love	38 Wealth	52 Money
11 Basic Needs	25 Material Possessions	39 Politeness	53 Unselfishness
12 Harmony	26 Patience	40 Generosity	54 Confidence
13 Health/Well-being	27 Morality	41 Equality	55 Freedom of Speech
14 Experiences	28 Righteousness	42 Service to others	56 Determination

Table 2: 56 most influential values, based on surveys conducted by Valuegraphics in 152 languages (2020)¹.

Our framework is also closely related to practical reasoning, a kind of reasoning that is legitimised and guided by values (Donaldson, 2021). It is going beyond a descriptive activity towards seeking reasons rather than causes, and justifications rather than descriptions, in a way that can integrate research methods with value creation in ways that offer relevant knowledge for practitioners and society (Donaldson, 2021). It offers a bridge between descriptive (what is), normative (what ought to be) and prescriptive (how to be) activities. Practical reasoning is also helpful for integrating economic value creation with more

¹ <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2020/11/values-graphic-care-behaviour-family-love-tradition-free-speech/>

fundamental and broad approaches to value (Donaldson, 2021). The philosophical field that studies practical reasoning is called Praxeology.

Bringing all these philosophical tenants of our value-based characterisation methodology, we propose a series of reflections on different fundamental areas (e.g., ontology, epistemology, deontology), driven by practical reasoning and especially by values.

1.4 Steps of the value-based characterisation methodology

Based on the previous foundations, here we describe the methodology for characterising the local value chains of the case studies. Specifically, we propose a series of reflection steps based on major philosophical dimensions involved in the pursuit of climate change adaptation.

1.4.1 Ontological step: Who are the key actors?

Ontology is about studying the nature of reality or existence. In our case, the ontological task focuses on the key agents of the problem at hand, by defining stakeholders and their network structure.

This first step defines who is who in the region, either people or organisations, e.g., society, research, innovation, industry, public administration, policymakers, civil society, culture, marginalised groups, environmental organisations.

Knowing stakeholders and their dependencies highlights whose values are central to the system (e.g., if small farmers are excluded, equity is undervalued).

Activity 1.1 – Identification of stakeholders:

- Identification of stakeholders based on their importance for climate change adaptation:
 - Key actors in the VC.
 - Emerging actors in the VC.
- List of actors stating their importance in the Current VC, whether they are gaining importance in the VC, and the importance in the future VC.

Example tools

- *Working with LL: Power-Interest Matrix (D2.1), Salience Model (D2.3).*
- *Complementary/independent research: Stakeholder Theory-based assessment.*

Activity 1.2 – Mapping stakeholders:

- Creation of stakeholder maps for the Current VC and the New VC, with their connections and dependencies.
- Analysis of the maps through Social Network Theory, with a focus on identifying emerging features, especially those related to the governance structures of the VC.

Example tools

- *Working with LL: Actor mapping.*

- *Complementary/independent research: Actor-Network and other social network-based assessment.*

Key questions

- Who holds power, influence or vulnerability in the VC?
- Who is an emerging or incipient actor in the VC?
- How do existing governance or coordination structures reflect ethical priorities (e.g., equity, sustainability)?

1.4.2 Axiological step: What are their values and interests?

Axiology deals with values and ethics. In our case, the axiological task looks at the interests and values of the stakeholders we identified in the previous step.

This step is important to explicitly clarify the interests (coincident or contrary) in the region. E.g., ecological, productive, leisure, cultural, societal, justice, among many others.

Analysing stakeholder interests reveals whose values dominate (e.g., corporate actors prioritising cost reduction vs. NGOs advocating for climate justice).

Activity 2.1 – Discover interest and values:

- Creation of a value list linked to the stakeholders of the VC.
- Analysis of values, interests, their conflicts and their power.

Example tools

- *Working with LL: Core values workshop².*
- *Complementary/independent research: Survey and semi-structured interviews.*

Activity 2.2 – Operationalise the interest and values. That is, making this step's information actionable in further steps.

- Expand the stakeholder map with information on key and conflicting interests and values.

Example tools

- *Working with LL: Actor mapping³.*
- *Complementary/independent research: Actor-Network and other social network-based assessment.*

Key questions

- What interests and values drive powerful actors?
- Are the stakeholders' values being prioritised equally?
- What trade-offs exist between economic efficiency, social equity and sustainability?
- How do conflicting values shape decisions? How are they addressed?

² Examples of core value workshops for [BBC](#) and [University of Houston](#), USA

³ Practical guides for actor mapping are [UNaLAB's](#), a simplified version of FSG (2017), and ITC (2022).

1.4.3 Epistemological step: What do they have?

Epistemology is about knowledge and understanding. Although identifying capabilities could be considered an ontological task, this step is more epistemological. We focus on gaining knowledge about factors that stakeholders can leverage to transform the VC and, especially, understanding how the stakeholders could leverage such factors.

This third step is about understanding the capabilities (current and emergent) that exist in the region. In other words, the resources, connections, expertise and other factors that every stakeholder could use to contribute to the transformation of the local VC.

This also involves the leverage of the socio-economic and environmental capabilities of the region. For example, environmental conditions, ecological characteristics, physical parameters, workforce training and investment capability, among others.

Activity 3.1 – Sensing current and emerging regional VC capabilities:

- Identification of current and emerging stakeholder's capabilities.
- Identification of current and emerging socio-economic and environmental capabilities of the region.
- Refinement of the identified capabilities through a Dynamic Capabilities lens.

Example tools

- *Working with LL: Adapted SWOT analysis⁴.*
- *Complementary/independent research: Survey and semi-structured interviews, Dynamic-capabilities-based assessment.*

Key questions

- How do values and interests shape our knowledge and understanding of current and emerging capabilities?
- How do power imbalances affect whose capabilities are valued?
- What are the capabilities of the most vulnerable actors?

1.4.4 Deixological step: What could be done?

Deixis is about referencing a particular time, place or subject relative to a context. In our case, we focus on the "situational worldview" of the VC stakeholders.

This step aims to leverage regional capabilities, considering the risks and opportunities associated with stakeholders' different worldviews about the current and emerging VC. This task should combine stakeholder experiences, field insights and technical perspectives.

Activity 4.1 – Sensing current and emergent risks and opportunities:

- Identification of current and emerging social, economic, sector and environmental risks and opportunities in the local VC and the region.

⁴ We consider that SWOT is the most convenient tool. It's popular and very flexible for adaptation. However, it needs to be adapted to the Dynamic Capabilities flavour of our value-based characterisation methodology. So, in this step 3 and from the SWOT perspective, the analysis focuses on identifying current and emerging strengths of the stakeholders and the region at all.

- Assessment of the identified risks and opportunities from a Contingency Theory and Dynamic Capabilities perspective.

Example tools

- *Working with LL: Adapted SWOT analysis⁵, Rapid risk analysis (D2.5).*
- *Complementary/independent research: Dynamic-capabilities or Contingency Theory-based assessments.*

Activity 4.2 – Seizing current and emerging regional VC opportunities:

- Ideation of potential business models or initiatives that could leverage the current and emergent capabilities of the regional VC to capitalise on its opportunities and overcome its risks.
- Assessment of the potential for VC transformation of the proposed ideas from a Contingency Theory and Dynamic Capabilities perspective.

Example tools

- *Working with LL: Strategy workshop.*
- *Complementary/independent research: Dynamic-capabilities or Contingency Theory-based assessments.*

Key questions

- What capabilities do we need to seize these opportunities effectively? Do we have them? Do we need to develop them?
- Which opportunities are most aligned with our existing and potential capabilities?
- How can we proactively shape some of these opportunities to our advantage?
- Which weaknesses and threats slow down or prevent us from seizing opportunities?
- What capabilities do we need to develop to overcome risks?
- How can we proactively shape some of these opportunities to our advantage?
- Are there any threats that could become opportunities?
- Do the proposed actions align with the interests and values of stakeholders?
- Could the proposed actions help to improve the situation of the most vulnerable actors? Could they make it worse?

1.4.5 Praxeological step: What are we going to do?

Praxeology deals with purposeful action. In our case, how we translate the previous step into value-driven actions for seizing current and emerging opportunities.

This step is about defining regional actions for transforming the VC to be taken in the medium and long term. In the case of FARCLIMATE, e.g., mid-2030s.

These regional actions should:

- Depart from what each participant is realistically able, and willing, to contribute (Praxeology).

⁵ In this step 4 and from the SWOT perspective, this analysis completes the one started in step 3, now focusing on identifying current and emerging opportunities, threats and weaknesses of the stakeholders and the region at all.

- Be understood, and shaped, as dynamic capabilities. That is, principles, practices and routines for reconfiguring, integrating and building the internal and external capabilities we assessed in steps 3 and 4. In other words, in step 5, we are looking for so-called dynamic capabilities that leverage the current and emerging internal and external capabilities we assessed in steps 3 and 4.
- Orchestrate the actors we assessed in steps 1 and 2 towards local/regional transformation of the VC.

Activity 5.1 – Regional actions for transforming the VC:

- Ideation of potential collaboration initiatives and platforms. Policy recommendations or other broad actions at the local/regional level for transforming the VC in the medium and long term.
- Assessment of the potential for VC transformation (through the leverage of internal and external capabilities) of the proposed ideas from a Dynamic-capabilities, Stakeholder Theory or Actor-Network Theory-based assessments

Example tools

- *Working with LL: Strategy workshop.*
- *Complementary/independent research: Dynamic-capabilities, Stakeholder Theory or Actor-Network Theory-based assessments.*

Activity 6.1 – Multi-perspective scorecard:

- Development of a multi-perspective balanced scorecard to combine the perceptions and achievements of the involved actors.

Example tools

- *Adapted Balanced Scorecard.*

Key questions

- How does the region adapt its resources and structures to maintain competitiveness?
- Do actions align with long-term social, environmental and ethical goals?
- How do our strengths allow us to seize new opportunities quickly?
- How can we proactively shape some of these opportunities to our advantage?
Are we asking for a fair contribution from the different stakeholders?

1.5 Recap on the value-based characterisation model

As recap (see Figure 21), ontology and axiology define stakeholders and their interests, epistemology and deixology help us understand the capabilities and the opportunities we can seize and, finally, praxeology turns all of the previous into a frame for action. This structure ensures that the community's values and knowledge drive the process, making it bottom-up. The philosophical steps provide a reflective meta-framework to address each layer systematically. It uses philosophical domains as scaffolding to systematically uncover and prioritise community-rooted values, knowledge, experiences and agency while resisting top-down abstraction.

Figure 2. Key steps in the creation process of the FARCLIMATE Transformation Hub

The value-based characterisation could be a proper continuous or recurrent exercise. A continuous update suggests an adaptive process, which is key in value-based approaches that remain relevant as values and circumstances evolve.

How should public administration or projects support all of this? Through awareness raising, training, small-scale pilot experiences, mentoring and networking activities. All these efforts should be updated continuously, identifying emerging competences that should be developed. These competences can be more effectively addressed through social innovation activities, making it possible to create societies more resilient against climate change.

2. Business modelling for climate change adaptation

This section introduces an additional method to guide business modelling for climate change adaptation and climate resilience, which may be particularly relevant for designing the strategy of socially and environmentally oriented enterprises.

This method establishes a theoretically sound “how-to” framework for helping practitioners model their strategy. The framework foundations come from business modelling, climate adaptation and strategy. The goal is to ensure theoretical generality, rigour (Osterwalder, 2004) and pluralism while prioritising practicality targeted to entrepreneurs.

This framework integrates existing tools, pivoting around the Business Model Canvas, with relevant insights from strategy schools of thought and practical recommendations. The idea is to bridge gaps between climate adaptation tools and entrepreneurial business modelling, integrating insights from both domains into a cohesive approach (Knott, 2024; Schlosberg & Collins., 2014; Trell & van Geet, 2019). Existing literature on business modelling, strategy, climate adaptation and social/sustainable entrepreneurship offers a myriad of valuable ideas for entrepreneurs (Daddi et al., 2018; Danese, 2024; Danese & De Marchi, 2024b; Huiskamp et al., 2022). Business modelling tools have also proved very helpful (Foss & Saebi., 2018; Geissdoerfer, 2018; Larosa & Mysiak, 2020; Massa et al., 2017; Rosenstock et al., 2020; Schoormann et al., 2022). However, as an emerging topic, fewer climate adaptation tools are available for entrepreneurs, and they usually focus on supporting bigger organisations (e.g., municipalities or mid-size firms).

This method uniquely bridges the domains of business modelling and climate change adaptation, offering a structured yet flexible tool for mapping business model logic in adaptation scenarios.

Compared to the traditional audience of business models, i.e., businesses of a certain size, social entrepreneurs face additional challenges, such as the complexity that brings their social-environmental missions and their constrained resources and time. With this framework, practitioners gain a structured methodology to navigate climate adaptation within business modelling, reducing cognitive and resource burdens.

In a similar fashion to what we did for the value-based characterisation methodology of Section 1, the approach for business modelling we present here is grounded in, and integrates, diverse ideas and findings from diverse organisational, managerial and strategic theories that we found relevant for business modelling for climate change adaptation. In addition to the ideas described in Table 11, which also applies here, we discuss in the rest of this introduction an additional recommendation: the ability to balance deliberate (planned) and emergent strategies—which we consider extremely important in strategy and, as such, in business modelling.

Balancing deliberate with emergent strategies

One of Mintzberg's central messages is that no single perspective on strategy is universally correct (Mintzberg et al., 2009). Each view has strengths, weaknesses, and contexts in which it flourishes or struggles. For example, plans provide structure and clarity in stable environments, but they can be too rigid in dynamic ones. Conversely, entrepreneurship thrives when visionary leadership and fast pivots are needed, but it can struggle with scalability once an organisation becomes more complex.

Mintzberg and other authors suggest that strategy formation is not the sole domain of rigid planning or ad hoc adaptation. Instead, they highlight how deliberate and emergent strategies can coexist, shaping how organisations navigate complex environments.

Deliberate strategies are those we consciously devise—setting clear objectives, drafting detailed plans, and carefully executing them. Emergent strategies, in contrast, evolve over time as we respond to new information and unexpected events. Understanding this contrast is the first step toward appreciating the multifaceted nature of strategy.

From a traditional standpoint, deliberate strategies follow the logic of planning, which seeks to chart a precise course of action, anchored in thorough analysis and forecasting. This assumes a stable environment and a high degree of predictability—making it ideal for organisations that operate with routine processes or within relatively static markets. The articulation that provides the deliberate approach provides clarity, ensures consistency, and can help optimise resources for well-defined ends. However, it also carries a risk: rigid plans may lose relevance if the external context shifts dramatically, leaving little room for adaptation.

On the opposite end of the spectrum lie emergent strategies. Here, strategy is “crafted” rather than dictated from above. Day-to-day decisions, responses to feedback, and real-time experimentation guide the way forward. Organisations adopting this perspective accept that uncertainty is inevitable; they embrace trial and error, treating each unexpected challenge or opportunity as a stepping stone to refine their strategic approach. Instead of purely reactionary, emergent strategy draws on collective insights, nurturing ideas that bubble up from different levels of the organisation and allowing them to coalesce into a coherent direction over time.

Nevertheless, a comprehensive, holistic view of strategy goes beyond toggling between deliberate and emergent modes. Different perspectives—be the already mentioned Stakeholder, Actor-Network, Contingency or Dynamic Capabilities theories—highlight critical nuances that inform and shape strategy. With diverse perspectives, an organisation is better equipped to anticipate changes in its internal culture, leverage power dynamics effectively, and adapt to shifts in the external landscape. This broad-based understanding recognises that strategy must account for both top-down planning and bottom-up innovation to stay relevant and effective.

2.1 Methodology for business modelling for climate change adaptation

We describe the methodology in five core exercises. Each exercise iteratively informs prior steps, ensuring the alignment of the strategy.

2.1.1 Problem-solution definition

Identify a problem and devise a solution. In a business or organisational context, identifying the problem might involve spotting a lack of efficiency, a dip in revenue, or an unmet customer need. The solution then becomes the basis of the strategy for tackling that issue—perhaps by introducing a new product, creating a new organisation, restructuring the team or adopting more sustainable practices. Entrepreneurs are unlikely to make meaningful progress without a clear problem and a potential solution.

Tool: Problem-solution statements.

2.1.2 Target scenario

This step depicts the anticipated scenario in which the entrepreneurs set the adaptation, focusing on eliciting the key social and environmental factors, the rationale of their venture and the time horizon.

Tool: System mapping of the context, actors and factors of the anticipated scenario, and from the triple bottom line perspective (economic, social and environmental). If required/interesting, a PESTLE analysis as support.

2.1.3 Competitive landscape of the target scenario

Now, we complete the anticipated scenario with the competitive landscape the entrepreneur would face. Analysing the competitive landscape with entrepreneurs is crucial for them to understand their market position and develop effective strategies.

Tools: Competitor Matrix, Porter's Five Forces.

2.1.4 Target business model

The target business model is the aspirational business model for the target scenario. The Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010) is used by entrepreneurs, large enterprises, nonprofits, and public organisations alike. Its versatility and clarity have turned it into a central pillar for designing strategies, launching new ventures, or simply understanding what makes an existing organisation successful. The fact that there are many variants of the Canvas now—some focusing on social impact, others on lean startup methodologies—speaks to its universal appeal. Regardless of the version used, the fundamental purpose remains the same: to clarify, on a single page, how all aspects of a business or organisation work together. Additionally, it represents the central elements of value creation, delivery, and capture (Cabanelas et al., 2013).

Figure 3. The Business Model Canvas.

Another useful step is to model the business ecosystems: In many industries, businesses are deeply intertwined in networks with customers, users, funding and other partners, suppliers, and complementary services.

Tools: *Business Model Canvas supported if required/necessary by the Value Proposition Canvas (Osterwalder, 2014); Business Ecosystem Mapping.*

2.1.5 Transition strategy

The transition strategy is for reaching the target business model and integrating the organisation's business development and climate transition strategies.

A transition strategy should be shaped on the grounds of the dynamic capabilities mentioned in Section 1.3.1. That is, principles, practices and routines for reconfiguring, integrating and building internal and external capabilities we assessed with the Business Model Canvas.

Tools: *Strategic workshop, Business Growth Map.*

2.2 Practical tips for business modelling

- Start with a brain dump: Gather a small cross-functional team. Spend 15–20 minutes jotting down ideas for each block without overthinking. The goal is to get everything onto the board.
- Prioritise: Once the entrepreneur has several notes, start grouping and prioritising them. If there are several value propositions, which one resonates the most with their target segment? If they are juggling multiple revenue streams, which is the most stable and sustainable?
- Iterate: Business modelling is meant to be revisited. As the entrepreneur gathers customer feedback or runs pilot programs, update the notes. If the entrepreneur realises that the proposed channel is too expensive or fails to reach their ideal customers, pivot accordingly.

- Keep it visual: The Canvas and other business modelling tools are designed to be displayed on a single large sheet of paper (or on a digital collaborative board). A single glance should give all the participants an overarching sense of how the initiative fits together.
- Test and validate: Especially for startups, business modelling is part of the lean methodology of “build-measure-learn.” Entrepreneurs should use quick prototypes or test campaigns to validate assumptions about customer needs, willingness to pay, or marketing channels. This is where doing entrepreneurship with the support of a LL comes in handy.
- “Stay true to your core”: Even though the entrepreneur might tweak certain aspects over time, like adding new segments or refreshing the brand, keeping the heart of their Value Proposition intact is usually best. A consistent identity fosters brand recognition and customer loyalty.

2.3 Further steps after the business modelling

The previous business modelling exercise could be used as a jumping-off point for deeper analyses. Here are a few ways to build upon the previous business models:

- In-depth Business Plans: Once the Canvas and the Transition strategy are set, the entrepreneur may need a detailed plan for investors or board members. This plan would detail budgets, timelines, and more granular marketing or operational tactics.
- Competitor Mapping: Use of a canvas-style framework to analyse competitors or peer organisations. Pinpointing how their value propositions differ, which segments they serve, and what channels they use. This comparison can reveal gaps or opportunities for the own strategy.
- Scorecards and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): From the Canvas, entrepreneurs can derive key metrics to track over time, such as customer acquisition costs, lifetime value, or churn rates. Nonprofits might track community engagement, donor retention, or impact metrics specific to the cause. For environmental initiatives, they may track objectives such as the ones we propose in Section 3. Others might move into building a comprehensive, balanced scorecard, where each quadrant (e.g., financial, customer, social, environmental) aligns closely with elements identified in the previous business modelling exercises. For instance, if the value proposition depends on continuous innovation, it could be helpful KPIs that measure how often they launch new features or improve existing products.
- Communication: Moreover, if entrepreneurs pitch their ideas to investors or grant-making organisations, they may condense the Canvas or the Transition strategy insights into a persuasive pitch deck. Their clarity helps present a coherent narrative: “Here’s who we serve, here’s what we do, here’s how we do it, and here’s why we’ll succeed.”

2.4 Recap on business modelling for climate change adaptation

When these elements work together, entrepreneurs can have a clear, inspiring strategy. Like a successful road trip, it departs with an important issue and charts a course to a meaningful resolution. This keeps everyone focused and motivated on the journey to success.

Some future work we envision using our methodology of business modelling for climate change adaptation is the following:

- Further work using this model with entrepreneurs should explore implementation barriers, logic gaps, training and capability-building mechanisms to strengthen entrepreneurial strategic capacities in climate adaptation.
- Another avenue for facilitating the implementation of business modelling is using generative AI or collaborative software to facilitate the business modelling exercise.
- Business modelling of a key specific sector for the case study, due to their weight in the local value chain or their potential for the new climate scenario. The goal is to identify the current and emerging sources of value creation, main competences and resources.

3. Indicators

CTA, UICN and UVIGO have conducted a preselection of indicators. We divide the selection into two groups:

- Self-assessment indicators (Section 3). These are indicators that the LL or other entities in the case studies could use to assess their own progress in their climate adaptation initiatives, projects or even at an organisational level.
- Statistical indicators (Section 3.2). These are statistical indicators at NUTS3 level or more granular that are available in Eurostat or that could potentially be found in regional and national statistical databases. We consider that these statistical indicators could be useful for the rest of the WP3 tasks.

3.1 Self-assessment indicators

The self-assessment indicators employ a 3 or 4 rating scale to describe how well the intervention matches the indicator. The ratings shall be interpreted as the following:

	Strong/good
	Adequate
	Partial
	Insufficient/unacceptable

Table 3: Self-assessment ratings.

3.1.1 Agriculture and fisheries self-assessment indicators

These are a selection from the indicators developed in D3.7 for a more detailed analysis of the value chains. The indicators of D3.17 come in their majority from the Sustainability Assessment of Food and Agriculture (SAFA) Framework (SAFA, 2014) of the UN Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities (Regulation 2020/852).

Indicator 1. Impacts to the atmosphere

Criteria	Answer (choose only one)
Has the company/project a plan that sets a target for achieving a decrease of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions?	<input type="radio"/> <i>There is a written plan, available to all stakeholders, with GHG emissions reduction targets, and steps have been already implemented towards achieving this objective</i>
	<input type="radio"/> <i>There is a written plan, but no steps have been yet made, this has not been put into writing or there is not available for all the stakeholders</i>
	<input type="radio"/> <i>There is no written plan</i>
If your company/project has a written plan for reducing GHG emissions, describe it briefly:	

Indicator 2. Impacts to the hydrosphere

Criteria	Answer (choose only one)
Has the company/project a plan that sets a target for reducing water consumption or water withdrawals?	<input type="radio"/> <i>There is a written plan, available to all stakeholders, with water conservation targets, and steps have been already implemented towards achieving that objective</i>
	<input type="radio"/> <i>There is a written plan, but no steps have been yet made, this has not been put into writing or there is not available for all the stakeholders</i>
	<input type="radio"/> <i>There is no written plan</i>
If your company/project has a written plan for reducing water consumption or water withdrawals, describe it briefly:	

Indicator 3. Implementation of biodiversity initiatives

Criteria	Answer (choose only one)
<p>What activities and practices have the company/project implemented that have effectively enhanced the functioning of ecosystem services, as well as the connectivity of ecosystems?</p>	<p><i>Some activities/practices have been implemented with the aim of enhancing ecosystem services and connectivity of ecosystems, such as:</i></p> <p><i>Cropland management</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Diversity-enhancing crop and grassland management</i> ● - <i>Creation and maintenance of habitat networks that facilitate exchange between populations</i> <p><i>Fisheries and aquaculture</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>Use of selective fishing gear and methods (e.g., turtle-excluding devices)</i> - <i>Promotion and implementation of the ecosystem approach to fisheries management and aquaculture development</i>
	<p>● <i>None activities/practices have been implemented yet for enhancing ecosystem services and connectivity of ecosystems, but there is a plan to do it</i></p>
	<p>● <i>None activities/practices have been implemented yet for enhancing ecosystem services and connectivity of ecosystems and there is no a plan to do it</i></p>
<p>If your company/project has carried out activities/practices for enhancing ecosystem services and connectivity of ecosystems, describe them briefly:</p>	

Indicator 4. Implementation of circular and bio-based initiatives

Criteria	Answer (choose only one)
<p>Which activities and practices have the company/project implemented that effectively replaced virgin non-renewable materials by recycled/reused/renewable ones in the operation and replaced synthetic inputs with natural inputs?</p>	<p>● <i>Some activities/practices have been implemented with the aim of replacing virgin non-renewable materials and synthetic inputs</i></p>
	<p>● <i>None activities/practices have been implemented with the aim of replacing virgin non-renewable materials and synthetic inputs, but there is a plan to do it</i></p>
	<p>● <i>None activities/practices have been implemented with the aim of replacing virgin non-renewable materials and synthetic inputs and there is no a plan to do it</i></p>
<p>If your company/project has carried out activities/practices for replacing virgin non-renewable materials and synthetic inputs, describe them briefly:</p>	

Indicator 5. Animal welfare awareness

Criteria	Answer (choose only one)
Which activities and practices have the company/project implemented that have effectively promote the health of animals, while reducing the use of veterinary drugs and preventing animal losses due to disease and injuries?	<input type="radio"/> <i>Some activities/practices have been implemented with the aim of promoting the health of animals, while reducing the use of veterinary drugs and preventing animal losses due to disease and injuries</i>
	<input type="radio"/> <i>None activities/practices have been implemented with the aim of promoting the health of animals, while reducing the use of veterinary drugs and preventing animal losses due to disease and injuries, but there is a plan to do it</i>
	<input type="radio"/> <i>None activities/practices have been implemented with the aim of promoting the health of animals, while reducing the use of veterinary drugs and preventing animal losses due to disease and injuries and there is no a plan to do it</i>
If your company/project has carried out activities/practices for promoting the health of animals, while reducing the use of veterinary drugs and preventing animal losses due to disease and injuries, describe them briefly:	

3.1.2 Forestry self-assessment indicators

Indicator 6. Impacts to the atmosphere

Criteria	Alignment	
	Yes	No
The use of pesticides is reduced and alternative approaches or techniques, which may include non-chemical alternatives to pesticides, are favoured, in accordance with Directive 2009/128/EC , with exception of occasions where the use of pesticides is needed to control outbreaks of pests and of diseases.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The activity minimises the use of fertilisers and <u>does not use manure</u> . The activity complies with Regulation (EU) 2019/1009 or national rules on fertilisers or soil improvers for agricultural use.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Well documented and verifiable measures are taken to avoid the use of active ingredients that are listed in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Annex I, part A, of Regulation (EU) 2019/1021(35), • the Rotterdam Convention on the Prior informed consent procedure for certain hazardous chemicals and pesticides in international trade, • the Minamata Convention on Mercury, • the Montreal Protocol on Substances that Deplete the Ozone Layer, • as classification Ia ('extremely hazardous') or Ib ('highly hazardous') in the WHO Recommended Classification of Pesticides by Hazard. The activity complies with the relevant national law on active ingredients.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Pollution of water and soil is prevented and cleaning up measures are undertaken when pollution occurs.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Observations:		

Indicator 7. Impacts to the hydrosphere

Criteria	Alignment	
	Yes	No
Environmental degradation risks related to preserving water quality and avoiding water stress are identified and addressed with the aim of achieving: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • good water status and good ecological potential as defined in Regulation (EU) 2020/852; • a water use and protection management plan, developed thereunder for the potentially affected water body or bodies, in consultation with relevant stakeholders. [Where an Environmental Impact Assessment is carried out in accordance with Directive 2011/92/EU and includes an assessment of the impact on water in accordance with Directive 2000/60/EC, no additional assessment of impact on water is required, provided the risks identified have been addressed]	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The activity does not hamper the achievement of good environmental status of marine waters or does not deteriorate marine waters that are already in good environmental status as defined in Article 3(5) of Directive 2008/56/EC .	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Observations:		

Indicator 8. Implementation of biodiversity initiatives

Criteria	Alignmen t	
	Yes	No
The activity is in accordance with the conservation objectives for areas: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • designated by the national competent authority for conservation; • in habitats that are protected. 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
There is no conversion of: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • habitats specifically sensitive to biodiversity loss or with high conservation value, • areas set aside for the restoration of such habitats in accordance with national law. 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
The forest management plan or equivalent instrument includes provisions for maintaining and possibly enhancing biodiversity in accordance with national and local provisions, including the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ensuring the good conservation status of habitat and species, maintenance of typical habitat species; • excluding the use or release of invasive alien species; • excluding the use of non-native species unless it can be demonstrated that: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the use of the forest reproductive material leads to favourable and appropriate ecosystem conditions (such as climate, soil criteria, and vegetation zone, forest fire resilience); - the native species currently present on the site are not anymore adapted to projected climatic and pedo-hydrological conditions; • ensuring the maintenance and improvement of physical, chemical and biological quality of the soil; • promoting biodiversity-friendly practices that enhance forests' natural processes; • excluding the conversion of high-biodiverse ecosystems into less biodiverse ones; • ensuring the diversity of associated habitats and species linked to the forest; • ensuring the diversity of stand structures and maintenance or enhancing of mature stage stands and dead wood. 	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Observations:		

Indicator 9. Implementation of circular and bio-based initiatives

Criteria	Alignment	
	Yes	No
The silvicultural change induced by the activity on the area covered by the activity is not likely to result in a significant reduction of sustainable supply of primary forest biomass suitable for the manufacturing of wood products with long-term circularity potential.	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Observations:		

3.1.3 Nature-based Solutions self-assessment indicators

These are a selection from indicators related to Nature-based Solutions or other IUCN standards (IUCN, 2020; Herzog et al., 2012; IUCN, 2023; Dussán-Lopez, 2023;), topic coordinated in WP5.

Indicators 10-13 can be applied in the design phase of the action/intervention.

Indicator 10. Current state of the ecosystem and drivers of degradation and loss

Criteria	Answer
<p>The intervention/solution directly responds to evidence-based assessment of the current state of the ecosystem and prevailing drivers of degradation and loss.</p> <p><i>Is the current state of relevant ecosystems assessed? Is this assessment at the appropriate spatial and temporal scale? Are the drivers of ecosystem degradation and biodiversity loss assessed? Does the assessment include field verification? Does the assessment take into account scientific and local knowledge? Do the action responds to the assessment and identified drivers of degradation and loss?</i></p>	● Yes. An updated assessment of the current status of ecosystems at the appropriate spatial and temporal scales is in place. The assessment includes information about the drivers of change and biodiversity loss. The assessment includes field verification and local knowledge.
	● There is information available about the current state of the ecosystems using secondary data and reference maps, not older than 10 years. The information of the ecosystem has been verified in general terms through field visits, with general inputs from local communities and traditional knowledge, where possible.
	● General information about existing land cover and land use is used for assessing the status of the ecosystems, at more general scales and not older than ten years. There is not validation at field level and data coming from communities or traditional knowledge.
	● No. There is no information available about general conditions of the status of the ecosystems at any relevant spatial or temporal scale.
Observations:	

Indicator 11. Biodiversity conservation outcomes

Criteria	Answer
<p>Clear and measurable biodiversity conservation outcomes are identified, benchmarked and periodically assessed.</p> <p><i>Are clear and measurable biodiversity conservation outcomes identified? Are these outcomes based on an understanding of the current ecosystem state? Are these outcomes applicable to the relevant period of time for the intervention? Are benchmarks for desired change in place? Are the conservation outcomes periodically assessed?</i></p>	<p>● Yes. The objectives include: specific and measurable indicator variables related to biodiversity and ecosystem integrity, the direction of desired change (increase, decrease, maintain), the magnitude of desired change (e.g., 80%) and the timeframe (e.g., within 5 years). Prior to initiating treatments, a monitoring and evaluation system is in place that includes the variables to be assessed, the frequency of assessment, the analyses that will be done to determine outcomes, and how information will be shared. Also prior to initiating treatment, a baseline assessment of the indicator variables has been conducted. Depending on the conservation actions proposed, monitoring and assessment yields enough information to indicate species or ecosystem recovery or a measurable extent of recovered areas, over a relevant period of time.</p> <p>● The outcomes include measurable indicator variables related to biodiversity and ecosystem integrity, but may lack specific details related to the magnitude of desired change (e.g., 80%) and the timeframe (e.g., within 5 years). Prior to initiating treatments, a baseline assessment has been conducted and a monitoring and evaluation system is in place, but may lack detail on the frequency of assessment, the analyses that will be done to determine outcomes, or how information will be shared. There is not enough information on ecosystem indicators for a relevant period of time.</p> <p>● The outcomes related to biodiversity and ecosystem integrity lack specificity. There is a general indication about relevant conservation outcomes and a monitoring system is under preparation.</p> <p>● No. The intervention lacks identified outcomes related to biodiversity or ecosystem integrity. There is no monitoring system in place and no data about ecosystem or species recovery.</p>
<p>Observations:</p>	

Indicator 12. Unintended adverse consequences

Criteria	Answer
Monitoring includes periodic assessments for unintended adverse consequences on nature arising from the solution/intervention.	● Yes. Possible adverse impacts of interventions on ecosystems, ecological process and species identified and actions to mitigate those impacts are mobilized. Specific measurable variables related to potential adverse impacts have been included in the baseline assessment, a monitoring and evaluation system of these impacts is properly implemented, and actions to address those impacts are in place.
<i>Is a monitoring and assessment plan in place for ecosystems, species and ecological processes? Is the monitoring plan based around measurable variables related to potential adverse impacts on nature arising from the solution, both direct and indirect? Are actions in response to those impacts in place? Is the monitoring plan properly implemented with measurements taking place at periodic intervals?</i>	● The intervention plan has identified possible adverse impacts on ecosystems, ecological process and species, and has included actions to mitigate those impacts, however lack of clarity on how actions will be mobilised and resourced. A monitoring plan for assessing adverse impacts is under development, including actions to counteract the effects of those impacts.
	● There is a general identification of possible impacts of the solutions at ecosystem level and plans to mitigate those impacts are in place.
	● No. There is no identification of potential impacts of the intervention and these impacts are not assessed.
Observations:	

Indicator 13. Opportunities to enhance ecosystem integrity and connectivity

Criteria	Answer
Opportunities to enhance ecosystem integrity and connectivity identified and incorporated into the intervention strategy.	● Yes. There is a detailed assessment of requirements to maintain or recover ecosystem integrity. Options to enhance the integrity of the ecosystem or connectivity, where appropriate, are identified and implemented. These options might include soil recovery practices, ecological restoration activities, isolation practices, or conservation actions for targeted species.
<i>Are the requirements to maintain or recover ecosystem integrity identified? Are opportunities to enhance ecosystem connectivity and integrity assessed? Are actions in response to these requirements and opportunities incorporated into the strategy?</i>	● There is a general identification of potential options to enhance ecosystem integrity or connectivity, where appropriate, and a plan to incorporate them into the intervention strategy.
	● There is a general identification of potential actions to enhance ecosystem integrity or connectivity, where appropriate.
	● No. There is no identification of any options to enhance ecosystem integrity or connectivity.
Observations:	

3.1.4 Other additional self-assessment indicators

In case studies related to agriculture, agroforestry or urban gardens, some additional specific indicators on biodiversity enhancement could be applied to the chosen practices, to be applied before and after the intervention.

Indicator 14. Genetic diversity of crops

Criteria	Answer
Increase in the number of different native species and varieties present thanks to new practices, actions or forms of management <i>Including cultivated and wild accessory species (e.g. left to grow wild between crops, in an agroforestry system covering the ground between trees, forming part of hedges or margins, or islands of wild vegetation between crops, etc.).</i>	There is an increase in the number of species/varieties of at least 30%.
	There is an observable increase of at least 10%.
	There is no observable increase in individuals.
Observations:	

Indicator 15. Genetic diversity of pollinators

Criteria	Answer
<u>Pollinators</u> (e.g. wild bees and bumblebees) Increase in keystone species after implementation of the chosen practice/solution/action (e.g. can be measured 1 year and 2 years later, by a simple protocol of direct observation of the number of individuals for a specified and standardised time)	There is an observable increase in individuals of pollinators of at least 30%.
	There is an observable increase in individuals of pollinators of at least 10%.
	There is no observable increase in individuals.
Observations:	

Indicator 16. Genetic diversity of earthworms

Criteria	Answer	
<u>Earthworms</u> Increase in keystone species after implementation of the chosen practice/solution/action (e.g. can be measured 1 year and 2 years later, by a simple protocol of direct observation of the number of individuals for a specified and standardised time)	●	There is an observable increase in individuals of earthworms of at least 30%.
	●	There is an observable increase in individuals of earthworms of at least 10%.
	●	There is no observable increase in individuals.
Observations:		

Indicator 17. Functional diversity

Based on the IUCN Urban Nature Indexes (IUCN, 2023).

Criteria	Answer	
<u>Species group or ecological function of interest across representative locations</u> There is an increase in functional diversity thanks to the action / solution / project. The aim is to assess ecosystem health and resilience by measuring functional diversity. Instructions: 1. Identify a group of species (may be a mix of taxa) according to an ecological function of interest such as: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • pollination • predation • ecosystem engineering • in situ bioremediation • temperature regulation 2. Select at least five representative locations across the project area. 3. Follow the example below or determine another measure of the selected function. 4. Measure the function at the representative locations. <i>Example: Pollination services can be estimated by counting the visitation rate of flowers in each location over a given period of time, or the rate of pollinated fruit/seed set in each location.</i>	●	Positive trend established per year
	●	Unchanged trend or Baseline measured
	●	Negative trend observed per year

3.2 Statistical indicators

3.2.1 Statistical indicators already identified for the selection of case studies

The following statistical data has been employed in D2.2 to select FARCLIMATE case studies. This data highlights data for the three sectors of interest (fishery, agriculture and forest) at the NUTS3/2 level.

We consider them key statistical indicators that can be used for WP3 tasks. They are helpful as NUTS3/2 level data from Eurostat. However, it may also be possible to gather this type of data, or similar, at a more granular level (e.g., municipality) in national and regional statistical databases.

This type of statistics could be useful for comparative analysis across case studies or European regions.

D2.2 provides a description of the indicators, but they are listed in Table 44.

Category	Indicator
Fishery	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential Environmental Impact of Climate Change • Percentage of coast regarding the perimeter of the region • Percentage of employment corresponding to the fishery sector (NUTS2) • Percentage of the coast included as Marine Protected Area • Adaptive capacity to climate change • Key Biogeographic Regions
Agriculture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential Environmental Impact of Climate Change • Potential Economic Impact of Climate Change on agriculture and forestry • Percentage of agricultural lands • Percentage of GDP corresponding to the agricultural sector (NUTS2) • Percentage of protected areas • Adaptive capacity to climate change • Key Biogeographic Regions
Forestry	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential Environmental Impact of Climate Change • Potential Economic Impact of Climate Change on agriculture and forestry • Percentage of forests • Percentage of forests (using it as equivalence of employment in forests) • Percentage of protected areas • Adaptive capacity to climate change • Key Biogeographic Regions

Table 4: Sectoral statistical indicators already identified for the selection of case studies.

3.2.2 Additional statistical indicators from Eurostat Statistical Atlas

We identified additional European-broad granular statistics to facilitate comparison across case studies or European regions. In this case, we found relevant statistics that can be consulted in, and imported from, Eurostat's Statistical Atlas⁶

Some of the data comes at a cluster level. Cluster types are groups of 1 km² population grid cells with similar characteristics.

Researchers can easily aggregate this type of information with common statistical packages (e.g., R, Python, even Spreadsheets), basically doing the following steps:

- a) Identify the relevant area for the case study.
- b) Identify the clusters for that relevant area.
- c) Gather cluster information from Eurostat.
- d) Create compound indicators for sets of clusters. Namely, one for all the clusters in the relevant area.

Table 55 lists the statistical indicators from Eurostat Statistical Atlas that we consider could be useful for the rest of the WP3 tasks.

⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/statistical-atlas/viewer/>

Category	Topic	Indicator	Granularity	Frequency
Demography	Age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Age (ternary colour for 6 compositions of age groups). Age, composition. People under 15. People aged 15-64. 	1 km ² clusters	Each census. Approximately an update each 10 years. Last, 2021.
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Median age of the population. Crude rate of total population change. Total fertility rate. 	NUTS3	Yearly.
	Population pattern	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type of cluster (urban centre, urban cluster, rural). Degree of urbanisation. 	1 km ² clusters	Last 2011.
Environmental	(Dominating) land cover	Continuous urban fabric, Discontinuous urban fabric, Industrial or commercial units, Road and rail networks and associated land, Port areas, Airports, Mineral extraction sites, Dump sites, Construction sites, Green urban areas, Sport and leisure facilities, Non-irrigated arable land, Permanently irrigated land, Rice fields, Vineyards, Fruit trees and berry plantations, Olive groves, Pastures, Annual crops associated with permanent crops, Complex cultivation patterns, Land principally occupied by agriculture with significant areas of natural vegetation, Agro-forestry areas, Broad-leaved forest, Coniferous forest, Mixed forest, Natural grasslands, Moors and heathland, Sclerophyllous vegetation, Transitional woodland-shrub, Sands, Bare rocks, Sparsely vegetated areas, Burnt areas, Glaciers and perpetual snow, Inland marshes, Peat bogs, Salt marshes, Salines, Intertidal flats, Water courses, Water bodies, Coastal lagoons, Estuaries, No data	1 km ² clusters	Based on CORINE land cover. Approximately an update each 6 years. Currently, 2018. Next update in 2026 for 2024 data.
	Drought impact area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Average drought impact area. Average drought impact area since 2000. 	NUTS3	Yearly
	Health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Premature deaths attributed to exposure to fine particulate matter. 	NUTS3	Yearly
Farming	Farm size	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Number of farms. Average economic farm size. Average economic farm size. Average physical farm size. 	1 and 5 km ² clusters	Yearly
	Agricultural area	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Utilised agricultural land. Share of arable land. Share of permanent crops. Share of permanent grassland. Share of fallow land. 	1 and 5 km ² clusters	Yearly

Category	Topic	Indicator	Granularity	Frequency
	Livestock	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Livestock units. Livestock density index. Bovine. Pigs. Sheep. Goats. Poultry. 	1 and 5 km ² clusters	Yearly
	Organic farming	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Area under organic farming. Share of organic farming. 	1 and 5 km ² clusters	Yearly
<i>Farming, Workforce</i>	Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full training. Basic training. Practical training. 	1 and 5 km ² clusters	Yearly
	Manager age	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share of under 40 managers. Share of over 65 managers. Ratio young/old. Average manager age. 	1 and 5 km ² clusters	Yearly
	Gender gap	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Share of female farm managers. Ration female/male managers. 	1 and 5 km ² clusters	Yearly
<i>Forestry</i>	Tree cover by dominant leaf type	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Tree cover by dominant leaf type (none, mainly broadleaved, mainly coniferous). Density of tree cover (various levels) 	1 km ² clusters	Based on CORINE land cover. Approximately an update each 6 years. Currently, 2018. Next update in 2026 for 2024 data.
<i>Related sectors</i>	Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Nights spent in tourist accommodation by origin of tourists (domestic, international). Change in nights spent in tourist accommodation. Nights spent in tourist accommodation relative to resident population. Nights spent in tourist accommodation relative to resident area. 	NUTS 3	Yearly
	Renewable energy production	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Renewable energy production from solar photovoltaic panels. Renewable energy production from onshore wind. 	NUTS 3	Yearly

Table 5: Additional statistical indicators from Eurostat Statistical Atlas.

3.2.3 Indicators that could potentially be found in regional and national statistical databases

Table 66 presents a list of statistical indicators that could potentially be found in regional and national statistical databases. We consider that these statistical indicators could be useful for the rest of the WP3 tasks.

Topic	Indicator	Granularity	Frequency
Demography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Average age. • Aging index. • Crude birth rate. • Average age at motherhood. • Average number of children per woman. • Natural population change rate. 	Municipal	Yearly
Workforce	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workers in the primary sector. • Workers in the fishery sector. • Workers in the forestry sector. • Workers in the agriculture sector. • Unemployment rate. • Employment rate over total population. • Employment rate over people aged 20 to 64. • Social Security affiliates. 	Municipal	Yearly
Economic indicators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GDP per capita. • Gross disposable income per capita. • GDP per employed person. 	Municipal	Yearly
Business demographics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Number of companies. • Change in the number of companies. • Number of companies (by number of employees). • Change in the number of companies (by number of employees). 	Municipal	Yearly
Training	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Educational attainment. • Literacy rate of adults. • Literacy rate of foreign adults. 	Municipal	Yearly

Table 6: Statistical indicators that could potentially be found in regional and national statistical databases.

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